

Antidiabetic effects of durian (*Durio zibethinus*, Family: Bombacaceae) leaves on alloxan-induced diabetic Sprague Dawley rats

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the anti-diabetic effects of durian leaves on alloxan-induced diabetic Sprague Dawley rats. About five (5) kilograms of fresh leaves of Durio zibethinus: Bombacaceae was obtained in Silang, Cavite, Philippines. The fruit leaves were obtained and washed with fresh water and damaged parts were removed. The plant samples were washed thoroughly with distilled water, pressed, air-dried, and were taken to the Bureau of Plant Industry of the Department of Agriculture of the Philippines in Manila for authentication. Alloxan monohydrate (Sigma Chemical Company, USA) was used to induce diabetes in mice and Glibenclamide was used as a standard hypoglycemic drug. Ethanol and distilled water were used for extraction of the plant materials. ACCU CHEK Performa Glucometer was used to measure the blood glucose level. The following chemicals were used for phytochemical screening test: Chloroform and ethyl acetate, hydrochloric acid, ferric sulfate, lead acetate and potassium ferrocyanide, petroleum ether 60-80°C, sulphuric acid, acetic anhydride and methanol and ferric. All the chemicals are of analytical grades. A total of sixteen (16) Sprague Dawley rats were utilized in the study. There were four groups in the study namely; No Treatment, Distilled Water as Negative Control, Glibenclamide as Positive Control, and Durian Extract. Rats were induced using Alloxan. Results show that the absence of a treatment will not reduce glucose level. The glucose level of Glibenclamide is significantly lower than distilled water and has no treatment. The glucose level of Durian is significantly lower than no treatment and negative control. Results also show that there is a significant decrease in the glucose level from post-alloxan to post treatment of durian. It also shows that the glucose level positive control is not significantly different from the glucose level of durian extract.

Keywords: Effect of durian, antidiabetic effects of *durio zibethinus* on diabetes, durian in diabetes, diabetic Sprague-Dawley rats.

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Introduction

Diabetes is a condition in which your blood glucose, often known as blood sugar, is abnormally high. The main source of energy is blood glucose, which comes from the food that you eat. Insulin, a hormone produced by the pancreas, stimulates glucose absorption into cells for use as energy. Your body may not produce enough insulin or use it properly at times. Glucose remains in the blood but does not reach the cells (NIDDK, 2016; Catania, 2021).

Diabetes is a chronic disease in which a person's blood sugar level rises too high. Type 1 diabetes and type 2 diabetes are the two most common kinds of diabetes. Diabetes type 2 is considerably more common than diabetes type 1 (Jelinek et al., 2016). In the United Kingdom, type 2 diabetes affects over

90% of all individuals. There are 3.9 million people living with diabetes in the UK. That's more than one in 16 people in the UK who has diabetes (diagnosed or undiagnosed). This figure has nearly trebled since 1996, when there were 1.4 million people. By 2025, it is estimated that five million people will have diabetes in the UK (NHS Inform, 2021).

Worldwide, diabetes prevalence increased fourfold, from 108 million in 1980 to 402 million in 2014. In the Philippines, the situation is no better where it is estimated that 1 in 5 Filipinos is a diabetic. The World Health Organization predicts that from 2.7 million in 2000, the number of diabetics in the country will reach 7.7 million by the year 2030. This hews closely to the current trend. The International Diabetes Federation has noted that diabetes has already exceeded the projected rate set for 2025 – when it is around 320 million diabetics worldwide (Wild et al., 2004). In 2015, however, there were 415 million already suffering from diabetes. Currently, there are four million diabetic Filipinos who are diagnosed, but even more worrisome is that there is an even bigger number of Filipinos who are unaware they have the disease (Tan, 2015).

Durian is widely distributed in Southeast Asia and is considered as “the king of fruits.” Durian (*Durio zibethinus*: Bombacaceae) commonly grows up to 30 centimeters long and 15 centimeters in diameter. Hundred grams of edible portion of durian contains water (64.99 g), protein (1.47 g), lipids (5.33 g), ash (1.12 g) and carbohydrate (27.09 g), fiber (3.08 g) (Delavajara et al., 2011)

Durian is also known for its cancer-fighting potential. The king of fruits contain high levels of antioxidants that fend off harmful effects of free radicals. The antioxidants in durian suppress oxidative stress and combat cancer cells. The high dietary fiber content in durian staves off colorectal cancer. Aside from this, the rich manganese supply in durian regulates and maintains blood sugar levels. This means that the king of fruit is especially beneficial to patients with diabetes (A Aziz & Mhd Jalil, 2019).

Durian is well-known for its numerous health advantages, including its capacity to stimulate the immune system, prevent cancer, suppress free radical activity, improve digestion, strengthen bones, reduce anemia symptoms, delay aging, lower blood pressure, and protect against cardiovascular disease. Durian has a number of small health benefits, including reducing joint inflammation, improving thyroid health, reducing headaches, and reducing feelings of sadness, anxiety, and stress. The excellent vitamin and mineral content of durian provides the majority of the health advantages. Vitamin C, folic acid, thiamin, riboflavin, niacin, B6, and vitamin A are all found in durian. Potassium, iron, calcium, magnesium, sodium, zinc, and phosphorus are among the minerals contained in durian. It also contains phytonutrients, water, protein, and dietary fiber, among other nutrients (Chian & Asohan, n.d.).

Methodology

Research Procedure

Sample and Collection

About five (5) kilograms of fresh leaves of *Durio zibethinus*: Bombacaceae was gotten in Silang, Cavite Philippines. The fruit leaves were gotten and washed with fresh water and damaged parts were removed. The plant samples were washed thoroughly with distilled water, pressed, air-dried, and were taken to the Bureau of Plant Industry of the Department of Agriculture of the Philippines in Manila for authentication.

Extraction Procedure

The leaves of *Durio zibethinus*: Bombacaceae were air-dried for one week under the shade at room temperature. The dried plant material were manually powdered finely and used for extraction.

Phytochemical Screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening of the plant extracts were carried out using standard procedures, to check for the presence or absence of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, steroidal compounds, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and anthraquinones.

Percentage Yield

The percent yield is the actual yield divided by the theoretical yield. It is calculated by dividing the experimental yield by the theoretical yield and multiplying by 100%.

Acute Toxicity Test

Acute toxicity test were done on both plant extracts after the animals had been fasted overnight while only taking water. The weight of each mouse were recorded before administering the extract. Randomly the animals were divided into a control and three treatment groups (separately for both extracts), each group consisting of five mice. The control group received only the vehicle (1% Tween 80) and each treatment group were receive orally the 70% ethanol and aqueous extracts of *Durio zibethinus*: Bombacaceae in a dose of 25, 50 and 75 mg/kg. Animals were kept under close observation for explicit toxicities and/or behavioral changes like restlessness, tremor, diarrhea, sluggishness, loss of weight, and paralysis at regular intervals for the first four h after administering the extract and then they were observed daily for two weeks for any change in general behavior and/or other physical activities. Food was available after four hours of administration of the extracts.

Induction of Experimental Diabetes

Male Swiss albino mice were fasted overnight (12-14 hours) and their weight and fasting blood glucose level recorded with a glucometer and then made diabetic by a single intraperitoneal injection (a volume of 1 mL/kg) of freshly prepared alloxan monohydrate solution (20 mg/kg body weight). Alloxan were prepared by weighing according to individual animal weight and solubilized with 0.5 mL sodium citrate at pH 4.5 before injection. Food and water were presented to the animals 30 minutes after administration of alloxan. After 48 hours of alloxan injection, plasma blood glucose level of each animal were determined by taking the blood from the tail and animals with a fasting blood glucose level above 200 mg/dL were included in the study (Sarian et al., 2017).

Experimental design

The animals were divided into four groups for the evaluation of fasting blood glucose level and oral glucose tolerance test with four animals in each group. They were treated with the plant extracts two days after alloxan injection excluding the diabetic control groups. Blood samples were drawn for measuring blood glucose levels from each group on days 1, 7, and 14 during the study period. Changes in body weight were also recorded. Groups 1 and 2 would serve as normal and diabetic controls (receiving only the vehicle, i.e., 1% Tween 80), respectively. Group 3 would receive standard drug (glibenclamide, 10 mg/kg per day orally). Group 4 would receive plant extract respectively daily in 1 mL aqueous solution using oral gavage for two weeks.

Experimental Animals and Treatment

The methods that are going to be used are based on the study conducted by Tafesse et al. (2017). Adult male albino mice bred in the animal with weights ranging from 24 to 35 g and eight weeks of age were used for the experiment. The animals were kept in cages made of polypropylene (randomly) at 23 ± 2 °C with 12 h/12 h light/dark cycle. Standard pellet and water were allowed to the animals throughout the experiment, except the fasting period. The care and handling of animals were in accordance with internationally accepted ethical guidelines for use of laboratory animals 1 mL/kg. Blood samples were collected at the time interval of 30, 60, and 120 minutes after administration of glucose. Statistical

analysis data were expressed as a mean \pm standard deviation. Differences among treatment group means were assessed by two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Average of Glucose Level for Baseline, Post-Inducement, and Post-Treatment

Group	Baseline	Post-Inducement	Post-Treatment
No Treatment	80.50	229.00	215.00
Negative Control (Distilled Water)	82.50	232.25	158.25
Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	91.75	233.75	109.00
Durian Extract	93.75	222.00	101.00

The table above shows the Average of Glucose Level for Baseline, Post Inducement, and Post Treatment. For Baseline, the average glucose for no treatment is 80.50, the average glucose for negative control (distilled water) is 82.50, the average glucose for positive control (Glibenclamide) is 91.75, and the average glucose for durian extract is 93.75. For Post-Inducement, the average glucose for no treatment is 229.00, the average glucose for negative control (distilled water) is 232.25, the average glucose for positive control (Glibenclamide) is 233.75, and the average glucose for durian extract is 222.00. For Post-Treatment, the average glucose for no treatment is 215.00, the average glucose for negative control (distilled water) is 158.25, the average glucose for positive control (Glibenclamide) is 109.00, and the average glucose for durian extract is 101.00.

Table 2. Test for Significant Difference in the Baseline Glucose Level

Compared groups		p-value	Significance
No Treatment	Negative Control (Distilled Water)	.854	Not Significant
	Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	.313	Not Significant
	Durian Extract	.238	Not Significant
Negative Control (Distilled Water)	Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	.403	Not Significant
	Durian Extract	.313	Not Significant
Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	Durian Extract	.854	Not Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

The table above shows the test for significant difference in the Baseline Glucose Level. Across all compared treatments, the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in the glucose level. Hence, the baseline glucose level for each treatment or group is not different from each other. This is a good indicator that they have started with the same level of glucose.

Table 3. Test for Significant Difference in the Post-Inducement Glucose Level

Compared groups		p-value	Significance
No Treatment	Negative Control (Distilled Water)	.843	Not Significant
	Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	.772	Not Significant
	Durian Extract	.670	Not Significant
Negative Control (Distilled Water)	Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	.927	Not Significant
	Durian Extract	.534	Not Significant
Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	Durian Extract	.477	Not Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table above shows the test for significant difference in the Post-Inducement Glucose Level. Across all compared treatments, the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in the glucose level. Hence, the post-inducement glucose level for

each treatment or group is not different from each other. This is a good indicator that the glucose level after post-inducement is at the same level.

Table 4. Test for Significant Difference in Glucose Level Between Post-Inducement and Post-Treatment Within Groups/Treatment

Compared groups	p-value	Significance
No Treatment	.599	Not Significant
Negative Control (Distilled Water)	.006	Significant
Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	.000	Significant
Durian Extract	.000	Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table above shows the test for significant difference in Glucose Level Between Post-Inducement and Post-Treatment Within Groups/Treatment. This table also shows the Hypoglycemic effect of durian based on the glucose level compared from post-inducement to post-treatment. For No Treatment, the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in the glucose level. Hence, the absence of a treatment will not significantly reduce the glucose level.

For Negative Control (Distilled Water), the computed p-value is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant difference in the glucose level between post-inducement and post-treatment. Hence, the glucose level when distilled water is treated is significantly lower that the glucose level before treatment of distilled water,

For Positive Control (Glibenclamide), the computed p-value is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant difference in the glucose level between post-inducement and post-treatment. Hence, the glucose level when Glibenclamide is treated is significantly lower that the glucose level before treatment of Glibenclamide.

For Durian Extract, the computed p-value is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is significant difference in the glucose level between post-inducement and post-treatment; Hence, the glucose level when Durian Extract is treated is significantly lower that the glucose level before treatment of Durian Extract.

The above results show that Glibenclamide is consistent in lowering glucose level. It also shows that Durian Extract has a potential hypoglycaemic effect.

Table 5. Test for Significant Difference in Glucose Level Between Treatments

Compared groups		p-value	Significance
No Treatment	Negative Control (Distilled Water)	.006	Significant
	Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	.000	Significant
	Durian Extract	.000	Significant
Negative Control (Distilled Water)	Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	.014	Significant
	Durian Extract	.006	Significant
Positive Control (Glibenclamide)	Durian Extract	.647	Not Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

The table above shows the test for significant difference in glucose level between treatments. This table shows if there is significant difference between Glibenclamide and Durian Extract in terms of glucose level and if Durian Extract can be a potential substitute to Glibenclamide.

For No Treatment compared with the rest of the treatments, the computed p-value is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant difference in the glucose level. Hence the glucose level of no treatment group which is 215.00 is significantly higher than the glucose level of Negative Control (Distilled Water) at 158.25, Positive Control (Glibenclamide) at 109, and Durian Extract at 101.

Negative Control (Distilled Water) at Positive Control (Glibenclamide), and Durian Extract is better than the absence of a treatment in lowering glucose level.

For Negative Control compared with Positive Control (Glibenclamide), and Durian Extract, the computed p-value is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant difference in the glucose level. Hence, the glucose level of negative control at 158.25 is significantly higher than the glucose level of Positive Control (Glibenclamide) at 109, and Durian Extract at 101. Glibenclamide and Durian Extract is better than Distilled Water in lowering glucose level.

For Positive Control (Glibenclamide) compared with Durian Extract, the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in the glucose level. Hence, the glucose level of Positive Control (Glibenclamide) is at the same level of Durian Extract. We can safely assume that Durian Extract is a potential substitute for Glibenclamide in lowering glucose level.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The absence of a treatment will not reduce glucose level. Glibenclamide is a proven drug that reduces glucose level. Durian extract has a potential antidiabetic effect. Glibenclamide and durian extract is better than distilled water in lowering glucose level. Durian extract can be a potential substitute to Glibenclamide.

The following recommendations were drawn based on the conduct of this study: a) Future researchers may use different concentrations of durian extract to make an extensive experimentation on the antidiabetic property of durian extract; b) The utilization of other standard drugs as positive control can be considered for future experimentation; and c) The researchers may also use time intervals to check the gradual change of glucose level.

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